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Therapeutic targeting in colorectal cancer for the treatment of liver metastasis: ETFRF1.

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The liver is the most common site of metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Measuring total transcription with RNA-sequencing and microarray in metastasis and the cancer (primary tumor) from which they are derived enables rational design and development of novel chemotherapies with optimized therapeutic index (9). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (10, 11) to measure total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer. We describe a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer, *ETFRF1*, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of liver metastasis in human colorectal cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the liver, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the liver to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the liver metastatic transcriptome in colorectal cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: ETVRF1.

Results

Figure 1: ETVRF1 is differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

I. Liver metastasis and primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer.

n=4 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer

n=3 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
144363	7.13E-03	0.639	-2.6908767	-1.7202169	134.18	ETVRF1	1677/19486	91.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the colorectum and in liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer, we discovered differential expression of electron transfer flavoprotein regulatory factor 1, encoded by *ETVRF1* in metastasis to the liver in humans with colorectal cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of ETVRF1 changed more than 90% of the human colorectal cancer (CRC) liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,486 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of ETVRF1 messenger RNA in CRC liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of ETVRF1 during disease progression in colorectal cancer.

II. Liver metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer.

n=10 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer

n=10 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
144363	5.34E-03	0.233	-2.7857731	-0.64999945	30.31	ETVRF1	976/15341	93.6

Through measurement of total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer as compared to primary tumors of the colon and rectum, we validated differential expression of ETVRF1 in human colorectal cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of ETVRF1 here changed more than nearly 95% of the liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 15,341 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of ETVRF1 messenger RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of ETVRF1 during disease progression and metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

1 Thus, differential and increased expression of ETVRF1 defines the liver metastatic transcriptome in
2 human colorectal cancer.

3 **Discussion**

4 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
5 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
6 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of ETVRF1, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for
7 efficacy in patients with liver metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the goal of identifying the
8 most effective inhibitors of liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer. A multi-kinase approach
9 delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter
10 strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, and target *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette
11 pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance
12 (12).
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Methods

We utilized GSE213402 and GSE179979 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer using RNA-sequencing data (public and published) and R-based computational methods.